

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS JUTE PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TOWARDS ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Dr. V. Santhi* & S. Niranjana**

* Associate Professor, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, PSG College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, PSG College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Eco-friendly products may seem to be more expensive, but long-term they are actually more cost efficient. Eco-friendly products tend to last much longer. These products are typically made from recycled materials and are sturdy, with standing most drops, kicks and dishwashers. Eco-friendly products may have larger sticker's prices, but since they last longer it is an investment that will pay off. In- today's world the planet needs our help. Our abuse and misuse of resources has put the planet in a difficult predicament, and we are the only ones that can stop the detriment. While it can be difficult to make a huge difference as one person, conserving resources and using eco-friendly products is a great way for each person to way for each person to participate in the preservation of our planet and eco system. During the era of great mughal emperor Akbar, poor villager's of India were used to white jute clothes. Since ancient times, roper and twines, used by Bengali. Indians are made up of white jute for varied household applications. Also Chinese paper markers have used all forms of plants like jute, hemp, cotton to make paper.

Key Words: Environmental, Eco- Friendly & Promotion of Jute

Introduction:

Human life cannot be thought of without an environment. The physical, chemical, biological, psychological and social factors in the environment are essential and play an important role in the normal functioning of a human being. It is only when these factors exceed certain limiting values there is an undesired effect on the physical, mental health or basic living of human beings. By environment, we mean, but only our immediate surrounding but also a verity of issues connected with human activity, productivity, basic living and its impact on natural resources such as land, water, atmosphere, forests, dams, habitat, health, energy resources, wild life etc.

Eco-Friendly:

This term simply describes a product that is not harmful to environment. However, it can get more complicated than that, as there are many factors of something that might be "harmful to the environment, so many different things can negatively influence the environment such as not using proper procedures when disposing of products. However, there are many benefit to using eco- friendly products that are not simply centered around the health and well being of the earth, but also the health and well being of your family.

It is an investment that will pay off along with the eco-friendly benefits, there are also personal benefits that coincide with using all natural products. Plastics, for example, are known to have BPA, lead and other chemical that can cause many different illness and diseases in both children's and adults. For adults the risk includes diabetes, heart disease and reproduction system abnormalities. For children, it can cause pre mature puberty, diabetes, stunted growth and autoimmune disorders. Eco-friendly, all natural products ensure safety from all natural products ensure safety from all dangerous chemicals and allows families to avoid risky additives that can cause any of these issue, using eco- friendly, all natural products ensure safety from all dangerous chemicals, and allows familiar to avoid risky additives that can cause any of these issue. Using eco-friendly products improves quality of life in terms of mortality, diseases and illnesses. They ensure the safety of families and the planet.

History of Jute:

Jute is known as the golden fiber of Bangladesh. It is a natural fiber comprised with silky and golden shine. It is one of the most cheapest and economical vegetable fiber after cotton, obtained from the skin or bust of plants stem. Recycle, 100% bio- degradable and eco-friendly jute has low extensibility and high tensile strength. Jute is the versatile natural fiber widely used as a raw material in may textile nonwoven textile, packaging, construction and agricultural applications.

From the 17th century to the middle of 20th century, the British Empire authority was delegated by the British East Indian Company which was the first jute trader. The raw jute was traded by this company. During

the start of 20th century, Muryaret Leannelly I was jute mill land- owner in Leundee who had set up first jute mill in India. The first consignment of jute was exported by east India company in the year 1793. In the country, Scotland, flax spinners were trying o clears whether jute can be mechanically processed. In the beginning of year 1830, Leundee spinners have determined spinning of jute yarn by transfiguring their power driven flax machinery. This leads to increase in the export and production of raw material in India. Jute industry played an important role in the economic development in India.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the customer buying behavior of eco-friendly product.
- To study the specification of buying behavior of jute product.
- To study the available of the jute product.
- To study the level of satisfaction to usage of jute products.
- To offer findings & conclusion of the study.

Types of Environment:

Natural Environment: Natural environment is that part of the planet earth, which remains untouched, and has not been invaded by man. It operates through self-regulating mechanism i e. Any chance in natural ecosystem brought about by natural process is counter balanced by chances in the other components of the environment, such as air, water, soil, radiation, land, forest, wildlife, flora and fauna.

Man Made Environment: Man is the most powerful environmental agent. He is the transformer of his environment. Man has altered the natural environment by overpopulation, urbanization, agriculture revolution, industrial revolution, dam building, revolution in communication and channelization of energy sources, such as hydrothermal and nuclear energy

Analysis & Interpretation: Analysis & interpretation of “A study on consumer buying behavior, towards jute products with special reference to environmental awareness” is presented based on the data collected from users of jute product. Following statistical tool were used in tune with the objective of the study.

- Descriptive analysis
- Diagrams and graphs

The percentage/ description analysis is a simple and basic tool to be used in the study involving primary data. It includes the number of respondent distribution under each category. As it is indicated in percentage it facilitates comparison and suitable chart are drawn in improving the understanding of the reader.

Know About Jute Product: Chart 1 describes the distribution of respondents based on knowing about jute product. Classified as self, friends and relatives, through advertisement and others.

Distribution of the respondents based on knows about jute product

The above chart shows that, out of the total respondents taken for the study 20(40%) of the respondents knowing about jute product through advertisement, 18(36%) of the respondent are knowing through friends and relative and remaining 12(24%) of the respondents are knowing about jute product by self. The results are presented in chart 1 for easy understanding. It is concluded that the majority (40%) of the respondents are knowing jute product through advertisement.

No of Years of Using Jute Product: Chart 2 describes the distribution of respondents based on no of years of using jute product. Classified up to below 1 year, 1-2 years, 2-3 years and more than 3 years

Distribution of the Respondents Based on No of Years of Using Jute Product

The above chart 2 shows that, out of the total respondents taken for the study 20(40%) of the respondents are using jute products more than 3 years, 15(30%) of the respondent using 2 years to 3 years, 10(20%) of the respondent using jute products 1-2 years. It is concluded that the majority of the respondent are using jute product more than 3 years.

Reference of Jute Product:

The chart 3 describe the distribution of respondents based on preference of jute product. Classified as passion, eco-friendly, attraction, specific design/ model others.

Distribution of the respondents based on preference of jute product

The above chart 3 shows that, out of the total respondents taken for the study 26(52%) of the respondent are prefer jute product as eco-friendly, 12(24%) of the respondent are preferred as attraction of jute product. The result are presented are presented in chart 3 for easy understanding It is concluded that the majority of the respondent are preferred jute product as eco-friendly.

Product to Prefer in Jute:

Chart 4 describe the distribution of respondents based on Classified as bags , hand crafts , door mates , foot wears , curtains, clothings and others

Distribution of the Respondents Based on Product to Prefer in Jute:

The above chart 4 shows that, out of the total respondents taken for the study 23(46%) of the respondent are prefer jute bags, 8(16%) of the respondent are preferred curtains in jute, 7(14%) of the respondent are preferred in hand crafts in jute, 5(10%) of the respondent are preferred door mates in jute, 4(8%) of respondent are preferred foot wears in jute and 3(6%) of the respondent preferred clothings. The result are presented in chart 4 for easy understanding. It is concluded that the majority of the respondent are preferred jute bags

Quality of the Jute Product:

Chart 5 describe the distribution of respondents based on quality of the jute product classified as excellent, good, best, and better

Distribution of the respondents based on quality of the jute product

The above chart 5 shows that, out of the total respondents taken for the study 30(60%) of the total respondents prefer to buy jute product, as good in quality 15(30%) of the respondents preferred excellent quality in jute product and remaining 5 (10%) of the respondents to prefer the quality of jute product is better. The results are presented in chart 5 for easy understanding. It is concluded that the majority (30%) of the respondents are prefer jute products is a good quality are preferred because of quality of jute product is good.

Place of Buying the Jute Product:

Chart 6 describe the distribution of respondents based on place of buying the jute product, classified as specified jute shop, exhibition, shopping malls and others.

Distribution of the respondents based on place of buying the jute products.

The above chart 6 shows that out of the total respondents taken for the study, 26(52%) of respondents are preferred exhibition for buying jute products, 14(28%) of the respondents are preferred shopping halls for buying jute products and remaining 10(20%) of the responded are prefer specific jute shop of their jute products. The results are presented in chart for easy understanding, It is concluded that the majority of the respondents are preferred expo/exhibition for buying jute products.

Findings of the Study:

- Majority (40%) of the respondents are knowing jute products through advertisement.
- Majority (40%) of the respondents are using jute products more than 3 years.
- Majority (52%) of the respondents are preferred jute products as eco-friendly.
- Majority (46%) of the respondents are preferred jute buyer.
- Majority (30%) of the respondents are preferred jute products because of quality is good.
- Majority (52%) of the respondents are preferred expo / exhibition for buying jute products.

Conclusion:

Jute as a renewable natural fiber is also bio- degradable and environmentally friendly. It is one of the few crops, which is growing in the monsoon season, and it is rotating with rice to restore the soil fertility and structure. The leaves of jute products enrich the fertility of the soil for sustained agriculture, and have good nutrition vales as vegetables. Use of jute stick as fuel and fencing material as substitute for wood prevents deforestation. Therefore, the increased global concern for the environment, the future prospects for jute remains high.

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